

EFFICACY OF DHANYAMLA DHARA IN THE TREATMENT OF AAMAVATA (RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is defined as chronic inflammatory disease that affects synovial joints. According to Ayurveda, *Aamavata* leads to pathology at big joints of body with stiffness, painful movement, inflammation, swelling at joints of Elbow, wrist, ankle and knee joint. Hence, Rheumatoid Arthritis can be compared to *Aamavata* which is one of the challenging diseases for the physicians due to its chronic nature and complications. The allopathic treatment provides the symptomatic relief which also give rise to many side effects, toxic symptoms and adverse reactions with more serious complications. A case of 42 years female diagnosed as *Aamvata* was treated with *Dhanyamla dhara* for 14 days. *Sahasrayoga* and *Dharakalpa* has described *Dhanyamla dhara* as *Purvakarma*. Ayurvedic pharmacodynamic properties, phytochemicals and bioactivities of the ingredients were also

gathered to identify the therapeutic values of *Dhanyamla*. After the treatment schedule, the patient was assessed clinically, functionally and haematologically and there was marked improvement in patient. Thus, *Dhanyamla dhara* proved to be very effective in managing symptoms of *Aamvata*.

KEYWORDS: *Aamavata*, *Aama*, Rheumatoid arthritis. *Dhanyamla dhara*.

INTRODUCTION

Aamvata is a clinical condition where vitiated *Vata dosha* along with *Aama*, formed due to suppression of *Agni* leading to *Aama sanchiti* which accumulates at bigger joint spaces after *Ahitahara and Vihara* according to Ayurveda texts. Even though *Aamvata* is one of the commonest joint disorders it has not been mentioned in *Brihattaryi*. *Aamvata* has been described in detail by *Madhavnidana*. According to *Madhavacharya*, it is systemic disorder where digestive and metabolic mechanisms are involved. *Aama* circulates throughout the body and vitiated by three *doshas*, leading to restricted joint movements.^[1] *Aamavata* is defined as the state in which simultaneously *Vata dosha* and *Aama* gets aggravated and localizes in the *Trik Sandhis* and produces stiffness in the body. The cardinal features of *Aamavata* are fatigue, heaviness of the body, fever, body ache, anorexia, excess thirst, indigestion, oedema, low back ache.^[2] In severe stages of *Aamavata*, pain is like scorpion sting which mainly affects legs, hands, ankles, thighs, sacrum and knee and other features including poor appetite, polyuria, vomiting, vertigo, constipation, stiffness in cardiac region, etc. In chronic condition deformity of the joints takes place. Treatment modality of *Aamavata* includes fasting, dry fomentation and intake of digestive medicines, purgation and administering enema for certain duration.^[3] *Aamvata* can be compared to many arthritic disease condition but its most of symptoms resembles Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA), a long-term autoimmune inflammatory condition that mainly affects synovial joints but can also cause extra-articular symptoms.^[4] RA is thought to affect between 0.3 and 1% of the world's population, with females in affluent countries being the most affected.^[5] In modern medicine different drugs such as NSAIDS, DMARDS, steroids and drugs acting symptomatically are given which have to be used for longer duration which can cause hazardous side effects on body. Therefore, Ayurvedic approach which has root cure to this condition is urgently needed. Considering *Aama* as a chief factor in pathogenesis of the disease, *Deepana, pachana, langhana, swedana, virechana and basti* is described as the management of the disease.^[6]

Parisheka is one of the thirteen types of *Swedana* described by *Maharshi Charaka*.^[7] *Parisheka Sweda* (Affusion sudation) is especially prescribed in the diseases where *Vata* is predominant. According to *Acharya Sushruta* and *Vagbhata* it can be categorized in to *Drava Sweda* (Liquid sudation).^{[8],[9]} In *Sushruta Samhita Dhanyamla* is mentioned as *Vata* alleviating drug which is suitable to use in *Drava Sweda* (Liquid sudation).^[10]

CASE REPORT

A 42 years old female came with the complaints of multiple joint pain especially in both ankle, knee, wrist joints since 5 years, on and off swelling over ankle and wrist joint since a year, morning stiffness for 1 hour, loss of appetite and constipation since 6 months, able to walk with the help of walker since 1 month, difficulty in performing the daily routine activity.

Past medical/ surgical/ family history: Patient had no history of DM/ HTN/ Surgical history/ Family history.

Menstrual and obstetric history: Regular menstrual cycle, patient was first gravida with one male child of 16 years age FTND.

Personal history

Diet- Vegetarian food, Spicy food

- Appetite- Irregular
- Bowel- Constipated
- Bladder- Normal

Sleep – Less

Addictions – No any

Eight-fold examination

- Pulse- Vata dominant
- Urine- normal
- Motion- constipation
- Tongue- coated
- Speech-clear
- Eyes- normal
- Built- moderate built

Systemic Examination: Systemic examination and all vital signs were normal.

On examination

- Severe bony tenderness
- Bilateral pitting oedema over legs
- Restricted movements of affected joints due to pain

- Walking time with walker for 25 feet was 50 second.

Differential Diagnosis - *Sandhigata Vata / Vatarakta*.

Diagnosis- The patient was examined according to Ayurveda as well as modern criteria. Then the disease was diagnosed as *Amavata* (Rheumatoid Arthritis).

Treatment advised- The treatment schedule was planned for 14 days. The patient was subjected to the *Dhara Sweda/ Parisheka* (affusion sudation) with *Dhanyamla* continuously for 14 days. Then the patient was called for follow up on 21st day.

Ingredients of Dhanyamla: Ingredients of *Dhanyamla* are given below according to *Sahasrayoga*.^[11]

Table No. 01.

DRAVYA	LATIN NAME	FAMILY	PART USED
<i>Tandula</i>	<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	Poaceae	Seed
<i>Pruthuka</i>	Pressed form of <i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	Poaceae	Seed
<i>Kulattha</i>	<i>Dolichos biflorus</i>	Fabaceae	Seed
<i>Laja</i>	Puffed form of <i>Oryza sativa</i>	Poaceae	Seed
<i>Kangubeeja</i>	<i>Setaria italica</i>	Poaceae	Seed
<i>Kodrava</i>	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Poaceae	Seed
<i>Nagara</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome
<i>Nimbuka</i>	<i>Citru acida</i>	Rutaceae	Fruit
<i>Deepyaka</i>	<i>Tachsporum roxburghianum</i>	Apiaceae	Seed

Method of Administration of Dhanyamla Parisheka The patient was made to lie down on the Droni (table). 1.5 L of *Dhanyamla* was warmed to body temperature. *Dhanyamla* was poured at a medium speed and at a height of four *Angula* (4 inches) above the body, in the morning. The medicine was repeatedly heated during the procedure to maintain the temperature. *Dhanyamla Parisheka* was done for 45 minutes per day. Fresh *Dhanyamla* was used on each day to perform *Parisheka*.

Assessment criteria: The patient was assessed on the basis of Clinical examination, Functional Assessment and Blood Investigations.

Clinical Assessment: Therapeutic effect was assessed using specially prepared Grading scale which is given below.

Table No.2.

Symptoms	Grade	Assessment Criteria
<i>Sandhi Shoola</i> (Pain)	0	No Pain.
	1	Mild pain, bearable in nature, comes occasionally
	2	Moderate pain, but no difficulty in joint movement
	3	Slight difficulty in joint movements due to pain or requires medication & may remain throughout the day
	4	Severe difficulty in moving the joint & pain is severe, disturbing sleep & requires strong analgesics
<i>Sandhi Shotha</i> (Swelling)	0	No swelling
	1	circumference of affected joint is less than 10%
	2	circumference of affected joint is greater than 10%
	3	circumference of affected joint is greater than 20%
<i>Sandhi Stabhadata</i> (Stiffness)	0	No stiffness
	1	0-10 min
	2	10-120 min
	3	2-8 hour
	4	>8 hours
<i>Sandhi Sparshashatva</i> (Tenderness)	0	No tenderness
	1	Subjective experience of tenderness
	2	Wincing on face of pressure
	3	Wincing on face with withdrawal of affected parts on pressure
	4	Resist to touch
<i>Angamarda</i> (Malaise)	0	No <i>angamarda</i>
	1	Occasional <i>angamarda</i> but patient is able to carry out routine work
	2	Continuous <i>angamarda</i> but patient is able to do carry out routine work
	3	Continuous <i>angamarda</i> and patient not able to carry out routine work
	4	Patient unable to carry out routine work
<i>Alasya</i> (Tiredness)	0	No <i>alasya</i>
	1	Starts work in time with efforts
	2	Unable to start work in time but completes the work
	3	Delay in start of work and unable to complete the work
	4	Never able to start the work and always take rest
<i>Gouravta</i> (Heaviness)	0	No feeling of heaviness
	1	Occasional heaviness in body but can carry out routine work
	2	Continuous heaviness in body but can carry out routine work
	3	Continuous heaviness which hampers routine work
	4	Unable to do any work due to heaviness

Functional Assessment

GRADE	0	1	2	3
Grip strength	200 mmHG and more	199 to 120 mmHG	119 to 70 mm HG	Under 70 mm HG
Foot pressure(in kgs)	25-21kg	20-16kg	15-10kg	<10kg

Walking time(for 25 feet in no of seconds)	15-20 sec	21-30 sec	31-40 sec	>40 sec
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Haematological Assessment

The patient was assessed for the following Haematological parameters.

- Haemoglobin (Hb %)
- C- Reactive Protein (CRP)
- Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR)
- Serum Rheumatoid Factor (RF)

RESULTS

The patient recovered gradually with the treatment. On application of *Dhanyamla Parisheka* she was totally relieved of Ankle & Wrist (joint swelling) and *Sparsha Asahishnuta* (tenderness). Also, she got relief in Pain, Stiffness of Knee & wrist joints. The patient was able to perform day to day activities with the normal range of joint movements. Her ESR, which was initially 130 mm/1st hour, had reduced to 35 mm/1st hour at the follow up. On the 21 day, Hb% also increased significantly. Therapeutic effect on the clinical features, functional and haematological changes are given in Table No 03, 04 and 05 respectively.

Table 3: Improvement of the Clinical features with the treatment.

Clinical Features	Before treatment	After Treatment (14 th day)	Follow Up (21 st day)
Sandhi Shoola (VAS)	4	1	1
Shandhi Shotha	3	0	0
Sandhi Stabhadata	3	0	0
Sandhi Sparshashatva	4	1	0
Angamard	3	0	0
Alasya	4	1	1
Gaurvata	4	1	0

Table 4: Changes in the Functional Ability of the patient with the treatment.

	Before treatment	After Treatment (14 th day)	Follow Up (21 st day)
Grip Strength	3	0	0
Foot pressure (in kgs)	3	1	1
Walking time (for 25 feet in no of seconds)	3	1	0

Table 5: Changes of the Haematological factors with the treatment.

	Before treatment	After Treatment (14 th day)	Follow Up(21 st day)
Hb (gm/dl)	10.6	10.8	11
ESR (mm/hr)	130	50	35
RA factor (IU/ml)	176.88	75	58
CRP (mg/l)	27.86	12.4	8.5

Ayurvedic Pharmacodynamic properties of ingredients of Dhanyamla In Ayurveda point of view the efficacy of drug is due to its pharmacodynamic properties. *Rasa* (taste), *Guna* (attributes), *Veerya* (potency), *Vipaka* (end product of the digestion), *Doshakarma* (action on body humors) and other properties of *Dhanyamla* are stated in the Table No 06.

Table 6: Ayurvedic pharmacodynamic & other properties of Dhanyamla.^[11-17]

Property	Description
<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Amla</i> (Sour in taste)
<i>Guna</i>	<i>Laghu</i> (easily digestible), <i>Teekshna</i> (penetrating)
<i>Veerya</i>	<i>Ushna</i> (hot in potency)
<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Amla</i> (sour at the end part of the digestion)
<i>Dosha Karma</i>	<i>Vata & Kapha Dosha Shamaka</i> (pacify Vata & Kapha Dosha), <i>Pitta Kopakara</i> (aggravates Pitta Dosha)
Other properties	<i>Deepana</i> (enhance digestion), <i>Jarana</i> (digestive), <i>Ruchya</i> (increase appetite), <i>Preenana</i> (satiating), <i>Mukha Vairasya Hara</i> (eliminate bad taste of the mouth), <i>Mukha Daurgandha Hara</i> (eliminate bad smell of the mouth), <i>Mukha Malahara</i> (eliminate dirty in the mouth), <i>Bhedi</i> (purgative), <i>Vibandhaghna</i> (laxative), <i>Hrudya</i> (good to the heart), <i>Jeevana</i> (sustainer of life), <i>Harshana</i> (exhilarating), <i>Jvara Hara</i> (febrifuge), <i>Shosha Hara</i> (eliminate dryness), <i>Shrama Hara</i> (relieve fatigue), <i>Klama Hara</i> (relieve exhaustion), <i>Sparsha Sheetala</i> (cold to touch), <i>Daha Nashana</i> (mitigate burning sensation), <i>Thrushna Hara</i> (mitigate thirst), <i>Vasti Shula Hara</i> (cures pain in the urinary bladder)

Bioactivities of the ingredients of Dhanyamla

Herbal ingredients possess different bioactivities. Scientifically proven bioactivities of the ingredients of *Dhanyamla* are given in the following table. [Table No 07]

Table 7: Scientifically proven Bioactivities of the ingredients of Dhanyamla.^[18-25]

Ingredient	Bioactivities
<i>Tandula</i> (<i>Oryza sativa</i>)	Anti-inflammatory
<i>Nagara</i> (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>)	Analgesic, Anti-inflammatory, Hypoglycaemic, Anti hyperlipidaemic, Antioxidant
<i>Nimbuka</i> (<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i>)	Antioxidant, Antiplatelet
<i>Deepyaka</i> (<i>Trachyspermum</i>)	Antihyperlipidemic, Anti-inflammatory,

involucratum)	Analgesic, Antipyretic
<i>Kodrava</i> (Paspalum scrobiculatum)	Antibacterial, Antitoxic, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant
<i>Kulattha</i> (Macrotyloma uniflorum)	Anti-inflammatory, Anti-hyperglycaemic, Anti-adipogenic, Anti hyperlipidaemic
<i>Kangubeeja</i> (Panicum sumatrense)	Cytotoxic, Analgesic, Antioxidant, Hypoglycaemic

DISCUSSION

In present study, patient got relief from the pain, stiffness, constipation and able to perform the daily routine activities without the support of walker. The main mode of treatment is to relieve the bio toxins (*Ama Dosha*) which in turn relieves the stiffness and pain, digestive fire was increased and constipation was relieved. Treatment modality acts as *Vatakapha* pacifying which in turn acts as barrier in the etiopathogenesis of *Amavata*.

Probable mode of action: *Dhanyamla* is a medicated liquid made out of cereals and few medicinal herbs. It is naturally fermented by *Sandhana kalpana* and has a long shelf life. It shows the properties of *Preenana*, *Sramahara*, *Klamahara*, *Deepana*, *Dahanashana*, *Vibandhaghna*, *Srotovishodhana*, *Jwarahara*, *Pachana* etc. This medicated liquid kindles *Agni* in dhatu level and helps in controlling of *Ama* (endotoxins formed due to faulty tissue metabolism) and also acts as *Pachana* to endotoxins present in different *Srotas* of the body. As it has *Laghu*, *Ushna* and *Tikshna guna*, it helps in alleviating the vitiated *Kapha dosha* and *Vata dosha* and removes *Srota rodham*. This helps in proper transportations of nutrients to each part of the body and result in increase in immunity. From a chemical perspective, *Dhanyamla dhara* is rich in phytochemicals such as flavonoids, tannins and hesperidin. Flavonoids are good antioxidant, tannins help in accelerating the healing process and hesperidin has capacity to prevent capillary bleeding and reduce inflammation. Thus, *Dhanyamla* is highly effective in *Kaphaja*, *Amaja disorders*, *Vata-Kaphaja* disorders especially in *Amavata*.

7. CONCLUSION

Administration of *Dhanyamla dhara* is highly useful and beneficial in combating the symptoms of *Amavata* (Rheumatoid Arthritis) especially pain, swelling, stiffness, and loss of appetite. The above treated patient is leading a quality life, for the past 1 year with minimal symptoms of *Amavata* (Rheumatoid Arthritis).

Conflict of interest- None.

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